

doi:10.5281/zenodo.14924790

Incidence Responsible For Divorce Among Married Persons In Port-Harcourt Metropolis: Implication For Counselling Psychology

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ABSTRACT

This study determines the incidents responsible for divorce among married persons in Port Harcourt metropolis, Rivers State: Implication for counselling. The study adopted descriptive survey research design. Five (5) research questions and (5) hypotheses guided the study. The population consisted of 500 married men and women. The sample consisted of 222 married persons. The researcher developed a self-structured questionnaire titled "Incidents Responsible for Divorce (IRD). Section A is made up of personal information such as sex, age, number of years in marriage, number of children and nature of occupation. Section B contains 25 items structured to determine incidents responsible for divorce among married persons. The instrument was validated by the researcher's supervisor and two other experts in Measurement and Evaluation and Guidance and Counselling in the department of Educational Psychology, Guidance and Counselling. Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port Harcourt. The reliability of instrument was obtained through the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient formula. A pilot test was conducted using 30 married persons in Port Harcourt metropolis. A retest was done after two weeks and answers provided show a high degree of consistency. The result of the pilot test gave a coefficient value of 0.92 using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient formula. Mean and standard deviation was used to answer the research questions while Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to analyse the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Keywords: divorce, married persons, counselling, marriage

INTRODUCTION

Amongst all social systems and structures, the family has undergone changes in many aspects. One of such change is the increasing rate of divorce. The most important unit of the society is the family but the rise in divorce rate has been predicted to disintegrate the family institution and the foundation of the society. The family is responsible for the nurturing of all children. It is a unit which ideally provides economic, social and psychological security to all its members. It is basically through marriage that a family is formed. Therefore, if marriages are being disrupted more often by divorce, the family could then be said to be going through serious crisis (Moore, 1994).

Divorce or marital separation or the dissolution of marriage is the final termination of marital union, cancelling the legal duties and responsibilities of marriage and the dissolving of the bond of matrimony between the parties (Mattoo & Ashai, 2012, p:113). Divorce is a remarkable development which has attracted global attention. Mekonnen, Kassa and Ayalew (2019) assert that divorce has severe effect on the family and the society. The psychological effect on the person who initiated it includes fear, distance,

impatience, doubt, resentment, guilt, blaming and fault finding. While the psychological impact on the receiver include shock, disloyalty, loss of control, ill-treatment, decreased self-esteem, anger, insecurity, a desire to get revenge. (Al-Ubaidu, 2017, p.3). Because of its psychological and social effects on the family and the society at large, government and non-governmental organizations have played vital roles in the elimination of marital separation by making divorce laws stricter.

Divorce affects the couple's children psychologically and socially. After divorce, the couple often experience effects that include, decreased levels of happiness, change in economic status, and emotional problems. The effect on children include academic, behavioural, and psychological problems. Studies suggest that children from divorced families are more likely to exhibit more behavioural issues than those from non-divorced families.

Marriage reflects the purposes, character, and customs of the society in which it is found. It is important for a transition of socio-economic values from one generation to the other. Marriage in Nigeria has its own historical background. Decades of colonialism in the country contributed significantly to the institutionalization of the practice. From the time Nigeria became a British colony till present, the celebration of monogamous marriage has been governed by statute law. However, the cardinal principle of the Nigerian statute is that it made the celebration of marriage a purely civil function, leaving it open to the parties to observe any religious ceremony they may think fit. Although today, celebration of monogamous is highly revered. (Nwogu, 2019).

Coontz (2006) in her book "Marriage, a History: How Love Conquered Marriage," pointed out that marriage was a way of getting in-laws, making alliances and expanding the family labour force. Love was not a criterion for marriage until recently. But as family plots and land gave way to market economies and kings ceded power to democracies, the notion of marriage transformed. According to her, it was really not about the relationship between the two parties. Its primary purpose was to procreate and ensure a clear inheritance and social relation. Coontz also pointed out that people established peaceful relationships, mutual obligations with others by marrying them. It is sufficient to say that there was more to marriage than meets the eye. Christin Mann in Nwogu (2019) buttresses that merchants often married as a means to secure their credit to inland distributors. It was a means of cementing social relations between clans, preserving tradition and culture, and codifying social customs.

Marriage is an important union where one shares feelings, responsibilities, and childbearing. It is said that singles are incomplete without their better halves; better halves, by God's design, are members of the opposite sex. Thus marriage fulfills many gaps of human needs and wants which leads to successful life. For marriage to take place, two individuals decide to form a household and live together. This yields higher personal welfare than living alone (Fafchamps & Quisumbing, 2006). It remains a deep-rooted culture among societies.

Cultures and values sustain marriage for long time. However, norms and cultures are dynamic. It is not static, it changes with the change of global condition. Makara (2009) agreed that global changes are affecting the world where we live in; these are technological, communicative and political situations. Through these changes, marriage values decline with increasing number of divorce cases. Ciardi and Mammini (2008) confirm that divorce has been introduced, and the value of marriages has declined. This is also revealed by Fagan and Churchill (2012). According to these scholars, Cultural Revolution plays a great role in the rise of divorce practices. As a result, divorce cases keeps increasing, particularly in industrialized western countries.

Divorce is much more complex than it appears on the surface. Ending a marriage relationship is not a one-time event; it goes through processes. Usually, a series of events and behaviors on the part of one or both spouses erodes the positive feelings toward one or the other or both. Over a period of time, one or both of the marital partners become convinced that the relationship is intolerable, or at least it is not working then as a solution the marriage comes to an end. (Fagan, 2012).

Societies have always had different views on marriage and divorce that the issue is influenced by the culture that one belongs to. Studies have indicated that there are many different and complex causes and reasons for divorce, each of them specific to that particular marital couple (Buzzle, 2013). In general,

Gersem (2006) concluded that all the divorce experience in the world today is as a result of one of the following: immaturity, infidelity, abandonment, lack of communication, physical abuse, drug and alcohol abuse, ego problem, sexual abuse, joblessness, lust, cultural and religious differences, crime, incompatibility, family background, failed expectations and the like. Other researchers like Cathy (2013) categorized the causes of divorce into three major parts based on her experience:

1. Laziness; there is a misguided belief that marriage will make one happy. Both parties feel relaxed and would not put effort into making each other fulfilled.
2. Lack of Communication Skills: this is a situation where a couple finds it difficult to openly express their feelings and listen to their spouse.
3. High Expectations: Expectations and laziness can go hand in hand when it comes to predicting whether a marriage will end in divorce. A lot of assumptions and presumptions are made by both men and women when it comes to marriage and what to expect from a marriage. These assumptions are based on many variables and problems arise when the outcome of marriage doesn't meet the assumptions or expectations. Communication before marriage can keep down any unrealistic expectations. Therefore communications play a role in the outcome of marital relationship.

Divorce is a serious experience that affects the whole family system particularly its impact on children is critical. Seblewongel (2009) pointed out that divorce is not an event that happened at a single point in time; it is accumulation of unresolved issues. Specifically, children whose parents divorced are at a great risk of incurring psychological and social problems that could affect all aspects of their lives than children whose family is intact. Children of a divorced family are exposed for various problems and risks they might find difficult to handle. Claiborne (2012) revealed that children of divorcees are more likely to be engaged in promiscuity (having many sexual partners), violence, crimes and other related anti-social and criminal activities.

Divorce is "usually perceived as the solution to difficult marital relationships irrespective of the repercussion on the couple, children, adolescents and society at large. Divorce is one of the most stressful life events a person can experience regardless of whether one sought the divorce or was unprepared for the divorce" (Ahiaoma 2013, p. 163). Divorce signifies the loss of an intimate relationship that also brought security and support. It also signifies a loss of hope and dreams as well as feelings of failure (Olaniyi, 2015, p.19). The rate of divorce in recent times has increased significantly and it has been the subject of discourse among social scientists from a wide range of disciplines in the last two decades. Unfortunately, insufficient number of studies in this area has been conducted. This study was undertaken to fill this research gap by analyzing the psychosocial variables that could lead to divorce among married persons as an implication for counselling psychology.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

The incidents responsible for divorce among married persons are enormous and some are underemphasized. Each of them is peculiar to that particular couple's marital relationship, their individual experiences and personal problems. Infidelity, financial problems and domestic violence, immaturity are important causes of divorce. Some women who are well educated and are well exposed to so many misconceptions about marriage are prone to divorce. Most of the time divorce has negative impact on the divorcee's families as well as on the society. The problems often affects the children as well even before parents divorce. This starts from the conflict between parents and painful divorce process. When children have got less attention, receive less emotional support, financial assistance, and practical help for academic support and encouragement, they may lose stimulation of socialization and this results to decrease of one's self esteem or pride, affection and social maturity. Those involved encounter psychological problems like depression, trauma, anxiety and unhappiness. Children suffer multi-dimensional effect. Those children involved are more likely to be less educated, experience poverty or socio-economic disadvantage, and develop anti-social behavior. This may include other behavioral problems like alcoholic addictions, drug abuse, get married or cohabit at earlier age.

Although there are studies/evidences on divorce that have been prominent in various literatures especially in the area of impacts of divorce, there is an existent gap in determining the factors of divorce on couple's

intention to divorce so far. Factors especially poverty, poor communication, lack of sexual satisfaction, and third party interference, domestic violence as incidents responsible for divorce have been undermined and underestimated by many researchers.

In the light of the above, this study intends to assess these incidents that could lead to divorce among married persons in Port-Harcourt metropolis as an implication for counselling psychology. In spite of the seriousness of the problem, there is no sufficient available study on the subject area to create awareness on the minds of individuals and to address the problems to those concerned in order to encourage a long lasting marriage that would stand the test of time. The researcher is motivated to assess the problems of divorce already mentioned above and its eventual impact on those involved.

1.3 Aim & Objectives of the Study

The aim of the study is to examine incidents responsible for divorce among married persons.

Specifically, the objectives of this study are:

1. To ascertain the extent of damage poor communication can cause in marriages
2. To evaluate the effect of lack of sexual satisfaction in marital union
3. To find out if divorce is a consequence of poverty
4. To discover the level of damage third party influence can cause in marriage
5. To assess the impact of domestic violence in marital union

1.4 Research Questions

1. To what extent does poor communication affect marriage?
2. How does lack of sexual satisfaction affect marital union?
3. Is divorce among married persons a consequence of poverty?
4. To what extent does third part influence affect marriage?
5. To what extent has partner violence affect marital union?

1.5. Research Hypotheses

- 1: There is no significant influence of poor communication on marital union among married persons in Port Harcourt metropolis.
- 2: There is no significant influence of lack of sexual satisfaction on marriage among married persons in Port Harcourt metropolis
- 3: There is no significant influence of poverty on the survival of marriage among married persons in Port Harcourt metropolis
- 4: There is no significant influence of third party interference among married persons in Port Harcourt Metropolis.
- 5: There is no significant influence of partner violence on marital union among married persons in Port Harcourt metropolis

1.6. Scope of the Study

Studying incidents that are responsible for divorce is crucial for preventing relationship breakdowns, and improving relationship quality. Therefore, this study is delimited to incidents responsible for divorce among married persons in Port-Harcourt metropolis. Analyses will also be delimited to responses of the respondents that will be sampled in the work.

1.7. Significance of the Study

This study can help prevent divorce among married persons. Understanding the factors that contribute to divorce can help identify individuals and couples who are at a higher risk of marital dissatisfaction or breakdown. This knowledge can be used to develop prevention and intervention programmes to help couples strengthen their relationships.

Secondly, identifying the factors responsible for divorce makes it possible to detect signs of potential marital conflict in the early stages. This can enable individuals, couples, and even therapists to address issues proactively, mitigating the risk of divorce and promoting healthier relationships.

In addition, this research will provide valuable insight into the dynamics of successful and unsuccessful marriages. By understanding specific variables associated with divorce, couples can work towards

improving those aspects of their relationship, fostering greater communication, satisfaction, and connection.

Furthermore, government bodies, social organisations, and policymakers can utilize research findings on the factors responsible for divorce to make informed decisions regarding resource allocation. By investing in programmes that specifically address the identified factors linked to divorce risks, policymakers can allocate resources more effectively and efficiently to support healthy marriages and families.

Moreover, it is an addition to knowledge. It is capable of generating further research in the area thereby expanding the coast of knowledge in some other schools or community.

1.8 Operational Definition of Terms

Incidents-In this study, this term refers to those things that affects behaviour and would contribute to a result and to a large extent affect the relationship between husband and wife. In order words, it refers to factors responsible for dissolution of marital union. Therefore, the two words will be used interchangeably.

Divorce the operational definition of this term refers to the legal dissolution or termination of marriage where the union between husband and wife is broken by the law.

Married persons - In the context of this work, married persons are people who are legally committed to each other (man and woman) as husband and wife. They are people who have been officially joined in marriage, or wedded and have legal agreement to be partners.

Predictors In the context of this work, this term refers to those conditions or situations that are signs of a possible divorce.

Strategies this refers to actions or systematic plan taken to achieve a successful marital relationship.

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Marriage

Marriage is popularly defined as the legal union between a man and woman as husband and wife. Marriage is a legally or statutory recognized union of two people (man and woman) as partners in a personal relationship. It is a legally and socially sanctioned union, usually between a man and a woman, that is regulated by laws, rules, customs, beliefs, and attitudes that prescribe the rights and duties of the partners and accords status to their offspring (if any).

Biramo (2022) posits it is a social union or legal contract that establishes rights and obligations between the spouses, spouses and their children, and the spouses and their in- laws. The institution of marriage was traditionally a union between a man and a woman. Depending on the values and norms of the society, there are different forms of arrangements to start family life. (Haviland et al, 2013). This implies that marriage is not just the union between a man and a woman but also the union between the couple and their relatives. The institution of marriage also gives the offspring a worthy status in the society depending on the norms and values of the society. Despite all efforts made by the community, divorce is unavoidable reality for many families

Marriage can be conceptualized in three ways: as an institution, as rite/ritual and as a process. As an institution, marriage consists of a set of patterned behaviours, expectations and relationships that are organized and endured over time. As a rite/ritual, it includes the ceremonies through which married status is achieved and as a process, It is a phenomena which is marked by gradual changes that could lead to ultimate dissolution through separation, divorce or death. (Thorton, 2007). It is sufficient to say that marriage is an institution that was created to last for a longtime but could face challenges that might lead to its dissolution through death or divorce. It also involves rituals that is in accordance to an individual's origin or community's tradition through which marital status is attained.

Marriage is a socially sanctioned union between a man and a woman which is accomplished by culture specific rituals and ceremonies. It is a socially approved way through which families are established. It is viewed as the most important event in the life of an individual between birth and death and signifies transition to adulthood. Marriage defines womanhood, manhood and adult status; it governs living

arrangement and is also central in the division of labour and authority within the family. Historically, the status of husband and wife is one of the most important transitions in people's lives.

Marriage results in the formation of family which is the primary unit of procreation, human interaction and linkages with the larger society. Marriage has also been defined by sociologists and anthropologists in the following ways:

Sociological definitions of marriage

According to Lowie (2013) marriage denotes those unequivocal sanctioned unions which persist beyond sexual satisfaction and come to underline family. The institution of marriage is beyond sexual satisfaction. There are relationships involving men and women without sexual gratification and involving a division of labour, e.g., between a brother and a sister, master and maidservant, or employer and employee, but marriage exists only when the economic and sexual are united in one relationship, and this occurs only in marriage.

According to Koos (2011), marriage is a dividing line between the family of orientation and family of procreation. Individual roles are different in these two forms of family. The roles in the family and orientation are different for the various stages as the child transcends from infancy to childhood and adolescent stage. The roles are not associated with duties and responsibilities. An individual enters into the family of procreation after marriage and plays the role of a husband, a father and an earning member. All these roles are associated with duties and responsibilities. The marital role is associated with primary relationships which are particularistic, altruistic and have a high degree of emotional involvement.

Lundberg (2012) defines marriage as a set of rules and regulations which specify the rights, duties and privileges of the husband and wife with regard to each other. To maintain equilibrium, stability of marriage depends on proper fulfilment of duties and obligations. The roles performed by both husband and wife are complementary to each other.

Anthropological definitions of marriage

According to Westermarck (2014) marriage is a relation of one or more men and women which is recognized by custom or law and involves certain rights and duties both in the case of the parties entering the union and in the case of children born of it. In this case, marriage may not just be between two parties but may also involve more than two people. In marriage sexual relations are legal.

Another anthropologist, defines marriage as a socially sanctioned union of male and female created by the society to approve the union and mating of male and female for purposes of establishing a household, entering into sex relations, procreating, and providing care for the offspring. (Mazumdar, 2005)

Legal definition of marriage

The meaning of marriage from the legal point of view implies that marriage is a binding contract between a man and a woman who join together their income, possessions and lives. It is a state of being united to a person of the opposite sex as husband or a wife in a consensual and contractual relationship recognized by law. Marriage is recognized by law and its dissolution can only take place through law through legal process of divorce.

Thus the institution of marriage is the socially and legally sanctioned way of procreation and establishing a family. Several other sociologists like Burgess (2010) opines that marriage is a system of roles and is a process through which primary relations are established.

The definitions above reveal that there are several elements of marriage which are universally accepted. There is a conjugation between two adults who cohabit, each spouse acquires kinship ties with the relative of the other spouse and their offspring are deemed to be relatives of both sets of relatives, the parties acquire status rights as a result of the marriage, the children born out of the union have special rights as legitimate, civil registration of the union is necessary and divorce is necessary before either party may enter into another marriage. Thus marriage gives rise to legal and social obligations. It does not only serve as a regulatory mechanism, it serves as a foundation for building families, kinship relations and clan.

2.1.2 Divorce

Divorce is the legal termination of a legal marriage between a man and a woman who are husband and wife. It is commonly known as the dissolution of marriage between a man and a woman. This means the two parties that were involved in that union no longer owes any marital duty to each other, spousal role has been terminated.

Mondal (2012) defines divorce as a formal (legal) and permanent form of breakup - termination of bona fide marriage. A bona fide marriage is a genuine marriage recognized by the law. Therefore when a genuine marriage has been permanently broken legally, it is considered to be divorce. If a husband and wife decide to separate and stop fulfilling their roles as spouses, it is illegal and unauthorized on their parts.

Bara (2019) defined divorce as the process of terminating a marriage or marital union. Divorce usually entails dissolving the bonds of matrimony between a married couple under the rule of law of the particular country or state. It is sufficient to say that divorce requires the sanction of a court or other authority in a legal process which may involve issues of distribution of property, child custody, alimony (spousal support), access to children, and child support. Monogamy is required by law in most countries, so divorce allows each former partner to marry another person.

Amadi et al (2001) noted that divorce maybe due to the quality of relationship that exists between the wife and her husband's relatives and vice versa, constant battering and maltreatment of the woman by her husband, infidelity, childlessness or bearing of only female children, poverty or emotional immaturity. Divorce is the process of setting both parties free from the bond of marriage which give them opportunity of new life.

For many centuries, marriage was regarded as virtually indissoluble in many societies, including India, where it was regarded as "sacramental" (religious). It was granted only in circumstances that were extraordinary. But now, almost all societies have made some provisions for divorce in certain situations. Today, marriage is less often seen as a sacred spiritual union, but more as a personal and practical commitment which can be broken if it fails. The trend is towards making marriage consensual. Attitude to divorce is changing speedily. It is no longer treated as an unforgivable sin. There was a stigma attached to divorce in the past. Now, it has become a more practical option for marital discord.

Walter (2005) maintained that divorce is the legal end of marriage and a relief to the highly stressed and tensed up couple. From his own perspective, divorce is relief from marital stress and tension. He added that the following are signs of divorce:

- Lack of value consensus in decision making.
- Presence of unequal distribution of sacrifice within the family set-up

Damaging of another's image

Dysfunction in marriage can be manifested in different forms. Mgbodile (2000) posited that that there is nothing like a perfect home but a home where you find a couple that have learnt to cover their human imperfections, Among others he noted the following as what cause marital dysfunction: power tussle between couple, infidelity, impatience, bad company or advisers and wrong use of words (inability to control the tongue).

There is no satisfactory answer to why divorce happens. Whenever two people interact, disagreement sometimes leading to conflict may arise at any point and one person or both may go to the extent of breaking relationship. This is true for all types of relationship including marital relationship. Unlike most relationships, however marriage involves civil, legal or religious ties that specify if and how the relationship can end. Divorce generally is an outcome of the failure of marital adjustment between a husband and a wife.

Research has identified several factors that may increase the risk of divorce. Some psychosocial variables that have been found to be associated with an increased likelihood of divorce include: marital dissatisfaction, personality differences, poor communication patterns, infidelity, financial incompatibility, emotional and physical abuse and in-law interference.

2.1.3 Incidents

Incident is an element that influences something or contributes to a result. This can also be referred to as factors. In this study, incidents encompass both psychological and social aspects of an individual's life, influencing their thoughts, feelings, behaviours, and interactions with others, marriage to be precise. They are studied to understand how they impact various aspects of human behaviour and well-being.

Incidents are variables which have positive and negative implications on an individual's quality of life, such as happiness, affection, anxiety or perceived stress, personality traits, emotional regulation. Bronfenbrenner & Morris (1998) opined that developmental process and outcomes plays a major function in marital crisis. They argued that as the individual grows, he/she develops a belief system, behaviour and attitude reflecting his environment that influences his/her interaction and this is carried into marital relationship. They concluded that spouses need daily psychological adjustment because individual differences play a major role in marital satisfaction/conflict.

Other general factors at the level of human society concerned with social processes that affect the individual include social support, loneliness, work environment, socioeconomic status and cultural background. These factors also affect the psychology of an individual (Preller, 2013). These encompass the broader social context within which individuals exist.

Human and social factors interact and influence each other. For example, a person's self- esteem may be affected by their social interactions and relationships, while their mental health may be influenced by social support or cultural norms.

Individual's differences are the psychological characteristic that distinguishes one individual from another. These differences can be seen in intelligence, personality traits, and values. If couples can manage their individual differences, they would enjoying a more satisfying marriage otherwise, it could lead to divorce.

Couples communication pattern is an incident that can affect married couples positively or negatively. If a couple is not able to communicate effectively with each other, the success of that marital relationship will begin to dwindle. According to Amadi & Amadi (2014). poor marital communication has been blamed for some other marital issues that brought about divorce or separation of a couple. Effective communication entails that couples discuss issues: they should be open minded so as not to create a communication gap that could lead to misinterpretation and further degenerate into crisis.

Sexual dissatisfaction is another factor. Poor sexual satisfaction in marriage can trigger crisis. If not properly and timely addressed, it could lead to extra-marital affairs thereby endangering the union. (Ambakederemo & Ganagana, 2006: Amadi & Amadi, 2014). This factor is a strong predictor of divorce and should not be overlooked. When couples cannot communicate their sexual desires to each other, misunderstanding occurs and the union might hit the rocks.

There are an array of factors responsible for divorce to be looked into in order to forestall or prevent divorce in a marital union. These factors can vary across individuals and different cultural and societal contexts. Therefore, research on these diverse factors helps to gain a comprehensive understanding of human behaviour and well-being.

2.2 Theoretical review

This study is anchored basically on the Social Exchange Theory (SET). An additional theory reviewed in this study is the Equity Theory.

The Social Exchange Theory was developed by George Homans, a sociologist. It first appeared in his essay "Social Behaviour as Exchange," in 1958. Homans studied small groups, and he initially believed that any society, community or group was best seen as a social system. To study that social system. To study that social system, it was first necessary to look at an individual's behaviour instead of the social structures individuals created.

It was by studying small groups that Humans began to see the rewards and punishments each member of the group got from the group and other members. Later, Homans began to explain further the most basic

level of social situations, called elementary social behaviour, which is atleast two people interacting, with one either rewarding or punishing the actions of the other.

Homans theorized social behaviour as an exchange of material and non-material goods, like time, money, effort, approval, prestige, power, etc, every person provides rewards and endures costs. People expect to receive as much reward as they give to another and will choose actions that are likely to provide the greatest reward. The theory posits that relationships are based on a social exchange where individuals weigh the costs and benefits of being in a relationship. In the context of this study on divorce predictors, SET can be used to examine the factors that contribute to the decision of individuals to remain in or terminate a marriage.

While there are several theories which might prove appropriate for a discourse of this nature, the theory of Social Exchange presents us with a better tool for interrogating the central issue of the study. Based upon the work of Blau (1964), the theory of social exchange is based on exchanges between parties within a social and human context where the behavior of individuals is based on the motivation of self-interest. Therefore, individuals who have a number of alternatives search for things and relationships that benefit them, searching for maximum benefit and the minimum cost in their interaction with others. Social exchange is organized through individual's expectations, acceptance and justice standards. Thus, we expect other individuals to meet our needs if we try to meet their needs based on what is right and fair for each of us. All social acts are based on social exchange or mutual benefit. Marriage is a system based on benefit, and couples look at each other in terms of good qualities and bad traits that they see in each other. That is, the more prominent the good qualities are in one of the spouses, the more positive and attractive aspects associated with the material and moral aspects are. In contrast, when these aspects are not present, partners would not benefit from the unjon and hence the tendency to end the relationship and go separate ways. The benefits are related to family communication, couple's behavior and personality, intimacy as well as family economics are all indicators of the adequacy of benefits for one or both spouses affecting the continuity or termination of the relationship by one or both spouse (Al-Gharaibeh, 2018).

Kelly & Thibaut (1978) further explains that the Social Exchange Theory of interpersonal relationships specifies how comparisons of costs and benefits of staying in relationship are continually made. It states that relationships are likely to dissolve when costs exceed benefits. Commodities being exchanged include sex, social support and food. Therefore, according to the social exchange theory, the consequent desire to stay in a marriage relationship will wax and wane, depending on how much each partner benefits from the relationship. In the final analysis, the relevance of the theory of social exchange is based on its ability to justify that like marriage, divorce sometimes achieves benefits. The social exchange theory holds that divorce offer solutions to many couples. Just as it harms one of the spouses, children or society, it also provides benefits to each of the parties at stake. Based on the social exchange, benefits and interests persists even in the worst of circumstances and even in the case of divorce. Thus, the management of the post-divorce relationship between the divorcees becomes more feasible especially when children are involved.

Several assumptions make up Social Exchange Theory:

- Social behaviours involve social exchanges of value
- People are motivated to retain some value (reward) when they have to give something up (cost).

People pursue social exchanges where they receive more rewards than their costs.

People will terminate relationships when they believe the costs are greater than the rewards.

When measuring rewards versus costs, people compare their expectations, previous experiences, or alternatives.

- People understand that "enough" rewards versus costs differ from relationship to relationship and within the same relationship overtime.

Equity Theory

Adams (1965) developed the equity theory. The equity theory addressed the issue of fairness in a relationship, Fairness is achieved when marital couples feel they get what they deserve from their marital relationship. Adams believes that such fulfilment increases interaction, dependence and love. The theory

proposes that a couple's motivation in any relationship is based on the quality of the contributions made to the relationship by each partner.

Equity theory is an extension from Walster et al. (1978) and Hartfield and Traupmann (1980) who developed the original equity theory from Adams (1965) stating that a partner would be unsatisfied if their relationship was over-benefitted or under-benefitted by either person. The person who receives more benefits will feel guilt and shame whilst the other partner will feel dissatisfied and angry. The longer this lack of equity remains, the more likely the couple will break up.

It is sufficient to say that equity theory suggests ties are sustained dependent on how any new or ongoing costs and benefits are realigned. Acceptance or unhappiness may result if something emerges that may be seen as overly costly relative to the advantages of the connection.

Due to inequity in a relationship, dissatisfaction in a relationship can cause it to end. For those who get more from the relationship, guilt might be a motivating factor, while resentment might develop for those relationships that require more effort to uphold.

It is important to note that Equity theory was originally proposed as the equity theory of motivation by Adams in 1963 with regards to work place. He asserted that employees want fairness between their dedication to a job and the outcomes they get. In essence, motivation is a sense of justice.

Some assumptions that make up Equity Theory:

An equitable relationship builds up stability.

People will dissolve relationship when they feel that the cost is greater than the reward.

Couples who viewed their relationship as equitable is more content and satisfied

People will prefer to remain in a more rewarding relationship that were they under benefit.

In addition, having understudied these theories, it is sufficient to say that both theories promote gender equity and fairness which is advantageous. It encourages couples to treat each other equally and fairly by not living one partner handle all the household responsibilities, for example.

2.4 Empirical review

Divorce is now a common phenomenon in our society. Where there is no longer mutual support, understanding and respect or love, the couple involved quits. According to various studies, the four most common causes of divorce are lack of commitment, infidelity or extramarital affairs, too much conflict and arguing, and lack of physical intimacy. The least common reasons are lack of shared interests and incompatibility between partners.

Relationship between Poor Communication and Divorce

Sarwatay and Divatia (2016) carried out a study on Interpersonal Communication between Married Couples on Planned Parenthood. They investigated the effectiveness of interpersonal communication among married couples and influence of friends, relatives and in-laws. The correlational research design was adopted. The study consisted of 370 couples selected through stratified random sampling technique. The finding of the study revealed that couples who had strong interpersonal communication had better understanding on the use of contraceptives for planned parenthood that those who had poor interpersonal communication.

This work and the study of Sarwatay and Divatia shares the same concern because they are both concerned about married couples. Good communication between couples is an ingredient of a successful marriage. In a situation where there is poor communication, it can be a predictor divorce.

Eseret et al (2015) carried out a research on poor communication and cognition on marital stability as expressed by married adults in Owerri metropolis. The study adopted a descriptive research design. The finding of the study revealed that there was a positive relationship between poor communication and marital conflict. Poor communication as a leading factor of divorce among married persons. One of the study's recommendation was that couples should practice effective communication at home.

Suleyiman and Zeudu (2018) conducted another study on Determinant factors on Couple Communication and Marital Stability among Adults in Assela Town, Oromia Region, Ethiopia. The study equally revealed that there was relationship between marital relationship and marital conflict. Most marriages had

ended in divorce because of poor communication. The study recommended that counsellors should provide counselling to couples before and after marriage consistently. The difference between the study and this study is the Area of study but their concerns are the same.

Relationship between Poverty and Divorce

Studies reveal that financial hardship is a major cause of family breakdown. Okakhume et al (2016) carried out a study on the Influence of Socio-economic and marital satisfaction among couples living in Nigeria. The study revealed that income and financial dissatisfaction was a factor responsible for marital breakdown.

Agboola and Oluwatosin (2018) carried out a study on Patterns and causes of marital conflicts among staff of selected universities in South-west Nigeria. The finding of the study revealed that 67.1% of the staff indicated that they experienced demand-withdrawn pattern. It found out that poor handling of family finances was considered as the most prominent factor with the highest result followed by communication gap.

Similarly Dean (2015) carried out a study on Materialism, perceived financial problems and marital crisis. It found out that there was a significant relationship between financial problems and marital crisis. Poverty is one of the root causes of divorce among married persons. If one's material needs is not met, it brings about financial dissatisfaction and to a greater extent, love might begin to deteriorate when priorities are not placed right.

Relationship between Poor Sexual Satisfaction and Divorce

Renaud et al (2017) carried out a research on sexual satisfaction and marital satisfaction in China. The study investigated the relationship sexual satisfaction and marital relationship. This study will also evaluate the effect of divorce on the children's upbringing and psychosocial adjustments in the face of a looming divorce.

Relationship between Partner Violence and Divorce

Kim and Emery (2013) investigate marital power, conflict, and marital violence in a National Representative Sample of Korean couples. The study adopted a correlational research design. The finding of the study revealed that there was a strong correlation between domestic violence and marital conflict which is most times exercised by men. It suggested that male dominant marital power structure should be used to achieve an equal marital formation. Kim and Emery's investigation shares the same concern with this study as it is one of the objectives the researcher intends to examine.

In the same vain, Onayose (2019) conducted a study on Prevalence of spousal abuse among married persons in South East Nigeria: Implication for counselling. The study examined prevalence of spousal abuse among married persons in South-East Nigeria. It was revealed that there was no domestic abuse but a high prevalence of verbal abuse among married persons. The study observed that high prevalence of domestic or verbal abuse is a threat to marital stability.

Similarly. Odebode et al (2018) observed in their investigation on Partners of domestic violence as expressed by married people in Ilorin metropolis Nigeria: Implication for marital and health counsellors. The study revealed that poor sexual relationship, poverty, infidelity, poor conflict resolution skills were the causes of domestic violence. The study's concern and this study also share the same concerns but the area of the research study is different.

CONCLUSION

The study reviewed the critical issues related to marriage, factors related to marriage divorce and some recommendations were pointed out to enhance better marriage in the future.

RECOMMENDATION

1. There should be better communication between couples
2. There should be sex and marital counselling before marriage
3. There should be dating in a relationship before marriage

4. Parents , pastors should not interfere much in the family, allow the couples to settle their problems
5. Couples should have the same place of worship and believes in one religion.

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